

Impact of ICT Enabled Distance Learning Models on Learner's Performance

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Abstract: In the present paper, we have discussed a comparative study of five Models Distance Learning (Taylor, 2001), as Correspondence, Multimedia, and Tele learning, Flexible Learning and Intelligent Flexible, evaluated with ICT based distance education tools. Flexibility (Time, Pace, Place), highly refined material, Advance Interactive Delivery and Institutional variable cost approaching zero were employed as variables. 209 students from secondary schools of Chhatisgarh state, India participated in the study. Amos software was used to study the fitness of models using structured equation modeling (SEM) technique. Correspondence model accounted for 23.6%, Multimedia Model 30%, Tele Learning Model 30.6%, Flexible Model 30% and Intelligent Flexible Model 30.7% of the variation in Learner's Performance. Inferences of the results of the present study are essential for instructors, learners as well as the institutions planning for quality education. The findings from the present study demonstrate the importance of ICT based distance education tools in predicting learner's performance.

Keywords: ICT tools, DE Models, Learner's performance.

INTRODUCTION

ICT and Education Technology

Information and Communication Technology acronym ICT, is time and again used as an extended synonym for information technology (IT), but is typically a added worldwide term that forces the role of unified communications and the integration of telecommunications, intelligent building management systems and audio-visual systems in contemporary information technology. ICT consists of all tools used to manage information and aid communication, including computer and network resources, communication middleware, as well as, the necessary software. ICT consists of IT as well as telephony, broadcast media, all types of audio and video processing and communication and network based management and monitoring functions (htt). It wires synchronous and asynchronous communication resulting in a series of educational applications such as video transmission, video conferencing, audio conferencing, computer conferencing, text chat, audio graphics, discussion boards and email. ICT formulates students to participate in a fastly changing world in which work and other activities are progressively converted by access to diverse and rising technology. ICT has the capacity to reach across the globe to those connected to global networks (Collis, 1996). ICT is making a

tremendous impact on education (Blurton & C., 1999). In the case of distance education, ICT enables teaching, learning and management of courses. Distance education or distance learning is described as "a process to create and provide access to learning when the source of information and the learners are separated by time and distance, or both" (Honeyman & Miller, December 1993). Distance education courses that require a substantial on-site presence for any reason (including taking examinations) were referred to as hybrid (Tabor & Sharon, 2007) or blended (Vaughan & D, 2010) courses of study.

It is necessary to determine the strengths and weaknesses of technology and understand the "appropriate context for technology applications if we are to use technology for effective teaching and learning" (Bates & A, 1995). Recent studies have focused on the nature of ICT-based education, which considers attributes such as tele presence, flexibility, interaction, active learning and collaboration (Harasim & Linda, Online Education: a New Domain, 1990c; Mason & Robin, 1998; Blurton & C., 1999; Harasim, Linda, Starr Hiltz, Lucio Teles, & Murray Turoff, 1996). The use of ICT in education initially increased rapidly; in some cases, it outpaced the research in the field (Harasim & Linda, Introduction to Online Education: Perspectives on a New Environment, 1990a). The increasing use of ICT in education and particularly in distance education, has

highlighted research in the field to conduct distance education into a new generation of ICT (Garrison, D.R., & T. Anderson, 2003).

Distance Education Models

Based on the mode of communication used, distance education were categorized into five generations (Taylor, 2001). These are the Correspondence Model, Multimedia Model, Tele Learning Model, Flexible Model and Intelligent Flexible Model.

Correspondence Model

The Correspondence Model refers to the first generation of distance education. For delivery of training and communication, primarily print-based modes of communication were used between the teacher and learners. One of the major drawbacks of the Correspondence Model has been the "slow turnaround in instructor/tutor feedback" (Collis,

1996). Communication and interaction amongst learners in this Model, however, was either non-existent or minimal (Nipper & Soren, 1990; Collis, 1996).

Multimedia Model

The Multimedia Model or second generation of distance education is characterized by the help of various modes and the rise of open universities or institutions primarily focused on distance education (Bates & A, 1995). In this Model, print-based modes are integrated with interactive videos, and audio- and videocassettes. Computerised learning also began to be used as part of Multimedia Model. Computerized learning included computer-mediate learning (CML) and computer- aided learning (CAL) (Taylor 2001). The concept of communication and interaction between the teacher and learners is similar to that of the first generation distance education, except for the

Table 1
Generations of Distance Education (Source : Taylor 2001)

<i>Modes of Distance Education and Associated Delivery technologies</i>	<i>Characteristics of Delivery Technologies</i>					
	<i>Time</i>	<i>Flexibility Place</i>	<i>Pace</i>	<i>Highly Refined Material</i>	<i>Advance Interactive Delivery</i>	<i>Institutional Variable Costs approaching Zero</i>
1 st Generation: Correspondence Print	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
2 nd Generation: Multimedia Print	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Audiotape	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Videotape	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Computer-based learning (e.g. CML/CAL/IMM)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Interactive video (disk and tape)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
3 rd Generation: Tele learning						
Audio-teleconferencing	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
Video-conferencing	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
Audio graphic communication	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
Broadcast TV/radio and audio-Teleconferencing	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
4 th Generation: Flexible Learning						
Interactive multimedia (IMM) online	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Internet-based access to WWW resources	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Computer-mediated communication	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
5 th Generation: Intelligent Flexible Learning						
Interactive multimedia (IMM) online	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Internet-based access to WWW resources	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Computer mediated communication, using automated response systems	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Campus portal access to institutional processes and resources	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

inclusion of individual telephone counseling and face-to-face tutorials (Nipper & Soren, 1990).

Tele Learning Model

The Tele Learning Model refers to the third generation of distance education and is characterized by the use of ICT-based synchronous modes of communication in distance education (Peters 1998, 2003). Communication modes used in this generation of distance education include video transmission, teleconferencing, audio graphics, audio conferencing and video conferencing linked either by fiber optic cable, Integrated Services Digital Network (ISDN), microwave radio frequency or satellite system.

One of the key advantages of this approach is its potential for delivering face-to-face instruction to distance learners in real time. Learners were able to participate in class in real time and communicate directly with their instructor or the author of the course (Bates & A, 1995). However, they lose the time and pace characteristic of flexibility (Collis, 1996).

Flexible Model

Fourth generation distance education also referred as a Flexible Model (Taylor, 2001). Fourth generation distance education is characterized by the use of asynchronous modes of communication. Interactive multimedia online; Internet-based access to World Wide Web resources and computer-mediated communication are some examples of the Flexible Model (Taylor J. , 1995). It provides distance learners with the freedom to learn at their own pace as in print-based distance education, while providing two-way instructor-learner and learner-learner interaction and access to the Web resources through the Internet (Taylor J. , 1995). ICT-based asynchronous modes not only offer distance learners with flexibility in terms of place, time and pace but also enable additional advantages such as instructor-learner and learner-learner interaction, and access to external resources through the Web.

Intelligent Flexible Model

Also, known as the intelligent learning Model, fifth generation distance education is a "derivation of the fourth generation, which aims to capitalize on the features of the Internet and the Webs (Taylor, 2001). Some examples of fifth generation distance education are interactive multimedia online, Internet-based access to the Web resources, computer-mediated communication using automated response systems

and campus portal access to institutional processes and resources (Taylor, 2001).

DATA

The data were collected from secondary students of the schools of Chhatisgarh state. The study was conducted in three districts of Chhatisgarh, i.e. Raipur, Durg and Rajnandgoan. Distance education tools, such as e-mail messages, chatting, online teaching, online assignment submissions, and online exams, were used to support their learning in the class. The course, Introduction to Environmental Science, was offered during the 2010-2011 academic year.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study examined self-reported opinions and perceptions of 209 school students of Chhatisgarh regarding education measured by replies for survey. The study included Likert-type items with response choices ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". Measurement on following variables was made.

Learner's Performance

The first section consisted of items about the role of the five delivery technologies as Print, Computer-based Learning, Broadcast TV/Radio, Computer Mediated Communication and Internet-based access to www resources in increasing the Learner's Performance. Higher scores in this part indicated better Learner's Performance.

Flexibility

This subscale assessed Learner's perceptions of the flexibility characteristic of distance education Models with particular reference to time, place and pace. Higher scores reflected positive beliefs about the adaptability of Learner's studying environment.

Highly Refined Materials

This section included items regarding the participants' attitudes toward the usefulness of highly refined materials through various sources. Higher scores indicated more strongly positive beliefs about the importance of highly refined materials.

Advance Interactive Delivery

This section specifies possible, advance interaction among available ICT based distance learning technologies. Higher scores indicate better interaction among technologies.

Institutional Variable Costs approaching Zero

This section included items regarding learner’s attitude towards lower cost of education. Higher scores indicate a reduction in tuition costs, increasing access to education on a global scale.

DATA ANALYSIS

Statistical analyses were conducted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences and Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) software. Structural equation Modeling (SEM) procedures were used to examine relationships among the variables. The structural equation analysis was conducted to assess the relationships among Learners Performance, Flexibility, Highly Refined Materials, Advance Interaction and Institutional variable cost approaching zero of distance education. The structural Model was tested by examining the path

coefficients, which are standardized regression coefficients. For each endogenous (dependent) variable, an equation was estimated by exogenous (independent) or other endogenous variables from another equation.

For a good model fit, different measures were used, to accurately represent reality; that is, they are measures of how well the model that we specified accurately represents the different processes and relationships at work (Kremelberg, 2011). The conventional measures of Model fit include significance level of chi-square value, the ratio of chi-square divided by its degree of the freedom (chi-square/df ratio), NFI (Normal Fit Index), CFI (Comparative Fit Index) and RMSEA (Root mean square error of approximation). The table below represents standard measures for good model fit (Kremelberg, 2011).

Table 2
Standard Measures for Model Fit Status (Source : Kremelberg, 2011)

S. No.	Measure	Full Form	Standard Model Fit Value	
1.	Chi-square/df	ratio of chi-square divided by its degree of freedom	<=5	Good
			5 to 8	Acceptable
			8 to 11	Marginal
			>11	Poor
2.	NFI	Normal Fit Index	>=.95	Good
			.9 to .94	Acceptable
			.85 to .89	Marginal
			<.85	Poor
3.	CFI	Comparative Fit Index	>=.95	Good
			.9 to .94	Acceptable
			.85 to .89	Marginal
			<.85	Poor
4.	RMSEA	Root mean square error of approximation	<=.05	Good
			.5 to .08	Acceptable
			.08 to .10	Marginal
			.10>=	Poor

Amos estimates regression weights and, from the estimates, it computes a stability index (Fox, 1980; Bentler & Freeman, 1983). If the stability index falls between -1 and +1, the system is stable; otherwise, it is unstable. The squared multiple correlation of a variable is the proportion of its variance that is accounted for by its predictors.

Correspondence Model’s Performance Evaluation

In this tested Non recursive Model observed endogenous variables were LearPerf and Flexible, while HiReMa, Time, Place, and Pace, were observed

as exogenous variables. The observed model fit value in comparison with conventional model fit measure is depicted in the table below.

Table 3
Model Fit Status of Correspondence Model

S. No.	Measure	Observed Model Fit Value	Standard Model Fit Measure
1.	Chi-square/df	1.381	Good
2.	NFI	.988	Good
3.	CFI	.996	Good
4.	RMSEA	.043	Good

Figure A (Structured Equation Modeling Output for Correspondence Model)

Stability index for Flexible and LearPerf variable is .003, Hence system is considered stable.

Table 4
Squared Multiple Correlations for Correspondence Model

Variables	Estimate
Flexible	.402
LearPerf	.236

Multimedia Model's Performance Evaluation

Figure B (Structured Equation Modeling Output for Multimedia Model)

In this tested Non recursive Model, observed endogenous variables were LearPerf and Flexible, while HiReMa, AdvInter, Time, Place, and Pace, were observed as exogenous variables. The observed model fit value in comparison with conventional model fit measure is depicted in the table below.

Table 5
Model Fit Status of Multimedia Model

S. No. Measure	Observed Model Fit Value	Standard Model Fit Measure
1. Chi-square/df	3.791	Good
2. NFI	.962	Good
3. CFI	.970	Good
4. RMSEA	.116	Poor

Stability index for Flexible and LearPerf variable is .073, Hence system is considered stable.

Table 6
Squared Multiple Correlations for Multimedia Model

Variables	Estimate
Flexible	.317
LearPerf	.300

Tele Learning Model's Performance Evaluation

Figure C (Structured Equation Modeling Output for Tele Learning Model)

In this tested Recursive Model observed endogenous variables was LearPerf, while HiReMa and AdvInter were observed as exogenous variables. The observed model fit value in comparison with conventional model fit measure is depicted in table below.

Table 7
Model Fit Status of Tele Learning Model

S.No. Measure	Observed Model Fit Value	Standard Model Fit Measure
1. Chi-square/df	10.319	Marginal
2. NFI	.896	Marginal
3. CFI	.904	Acceptable
4. RMSEA	.212	Poor

Table 8
Squared Multiple Correlations for Tele Learning Model

Variables	Estimate
AdvInter	.000
HiReMa	.000
LearPerf	.306

Flexible Model's Performance Evaluation

Figure D (Structured Equation Modeling Output for Flexible Model)

In this tested Non recursive Model, observed endogenous variables were LearPerf and Flexible, while HiReMa, AdvInter, Time, Place, and Pace, were observed as exogenous variables. The observed model fit value in comparison with conventional model fit measure is depicted in table below.

Table 9
Model Fit Status of Flexible Model

S.No.	Measure	Observed Model Fit Value	Standard Model Fit Measure
1.	Chi-square/df	3.791	Good
2.	NFI	.962	Good
3.	CFI	.970	Good
4.	RMSEA	.116	Poor

Stability index for Flexible and LearPerf variable is .073, Hence system is considered stable.

Table 10
Squared Multiple Correlations for Flexible Model

Variables	Estimate
Flexible	.317
Lear Perf	.300

Intelligent Flexible Model's Performance Evaluation

In this tested Non recursive Model, observed endogenous variables were LearPerf and Flexible, while HiReMa, AdvInter, InstZero, Time, Place, and Pace were observed as exogenous variables. The observed model fit value in comparison with conventional model fit measure is depicted in the table below.

Table 11
Model Fit Status of Intelligent Flexible Model

S.No.	Measure	Observed Model Fit Value	Standard Model Fit Measure
1.	Chi-square/df	2.887	Good
2.	NFI	.976	Good
3.	CFI	.983	Good
4.	RMSEA	.095	Good

Stability index for Flexible and LearPerf variable is .063, Hence system is considered stable.

Table 12
Squared Multiple Correlations for Intelligent Flexible Model

Variables	Estimate
Flexible	.317
LearPerf	.307

FINDINGS AND RESULT

In Correspondence Modeevaluation combination of Time, place, pace and highly refined material accounted for 23.6% of the variation in Learner's

performance. In Multimedia Model evaluation combination of highly refined material, Advance Interaction, Time, Place and Pace accounted for 30% of the variation in Learner's Performance. In Tele Learning Model evaluation combination of highly refined material and Advance Interaction accounted for 30.6% of the variation in Learners Performance. In Flexible Model evaluation combination of highly refined material, Advance Interaction, Time, Place and Pace accounted for 30.0% of the variation in Learner's Performance. Lastly in Intelligent Flexible Model evaluation combination of highly refined material, Advance Interaction, Institutional variable cost to zero accounted for 30.7% of the variation in Learner's Performance.

DISCUSSION

The findings from the present study demonstrate the importance of ICT based distance education tools in predicting learner's performance from their studying experience. Students' online readiness, motivation, and attitude are keys for the success of any training program (Ardito, *et al.*, 2006). Hence, technical issues should not become an obstacle to learner's education. To improve learners' performance, they need to be supported both technically and scientifically.

The results of this study highlight the critical part of perceived attributes in the learner's performance from ICT tools. The literature suggests that perceived attributes and perceived performance may increase students' use of Internet resources (Lee, M., & Cheung, 2005). Thus, high learner performance from their learning experience may lead to further promise in class activities and ultimately in higher levels of use of learning environments. The findings from this study clearly show that a training curriculum should provide learners with considerable flexibility in interacting with their instructor, classmates, and the course content. Indeed, flexible course structure is a key strategy to overcome the intrinsic and extrinsic barriers to e-learning (Jones, Packham, Miller, & Jones, 2004).

CONCLUSIONS

The availability of the six attributes (Time, Place, Pace, Highly Refined Material, Advance Interaction, Institutional variable cost approaching zero) may lead to greater applications of education. Findings from the present study suggest that learners' performance can be improved with mentioned attributes of ICT based distance education Models. Instructors of education need to focus upon preparing students in

using a variety of ICT technologies and aware of the benefits of online learning. Well designed and sensibly applied learning environments are required to meet the requirements and potentials of learners. Learning environments can be facilitated through activities that extend learners' level of ICT knowledge and emphasize the flexibility and usefulness characteristics of education. The results of this study suggest that these attributes are needed to promote student satisfaction with the education. Hence, institutions and instructors should pay attention to the variables affecting student delight with education courses. Then, the learning environment might be more spontaneous, attractive, and ultimately more informative.

In addition, future studies might focus on their applicability to other areas and settings. These efforts will be beneficial to the improvement of the model and the continued development of research and practice in education. There is no doubt that many factors may affect learner performance in learning environments. Further modification of the models could identify more factors that educators can modify to improve the quality of their courses.

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